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NAIP modulation during embryonic development.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We observed NAIP modulation as a lineage commitment cooperating event in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

Citations

1. Listen, P., Roy, N., Tamai, K., Lefebvre, C., Baird, S., Cherton-Horvat, G., Farahani, R., McLean, M., Lkeda, J.E., Mackenzie, A. and Korneluk, R.G., 1996. Suppression of apoptosis in mammalian cells by NAIP and a related family of IAP genes. Nature, 379(6563), pp.349-353.